

REFERENCES: Review of broadband electrical behavior of clays: critical synthesis and comparison of experimental signatures and models

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Glossary

General electrical quantities

- σ^* : complex electrical conductivity
- σ' : in-phase (real) conductivity
- σ'' : quadrature (imaginary) conductivity
- ε^* : complex dielectric permittivity
- ε' : dielectric storage component
- ε'' : dielectric loss component
- ρ^* : complex resistivity
- ω : angular frequency ($= 2\pi f$)
- M^* : electric modulus formalism used to reduce electrode polarization effects (Cadène et al. 2006; Saltas et al. 2008)

Relaxation terminology

- τ : characteristic relaxation time of a polarization process
- τ_{EDL} : EDL polarization relaxation time
- τ_{MW} : Maxwell-Wagner relaxation time
- τ_{CC} : Cole–Cole characteristic relaxation time
- τ_p : Pelton-model relaxation time
- τ_α : intermediate relaxation reported in GDR/CPCM dielectric models
- τ_D : diffusion-related relaxation time

Main acronyms

- SIP: Spectral Induced Polarization
- BDS: Broadband Dielectric Spectroscopy
- EDL: Electrical Double Layer
- MW: Maxwell–Wagner polarization
- CTL: Coaxial Transmission Line
- OE probe: Open-ended coaxial probe
- CEC: Cation Exchange Capacity
- SSA: Specific Surface Area
- CRIM: Complex Refractive Index Model
- CPCM: Combined Permittivity and Conductivity Model
- GDR: Generalized Dielectric Response
- VNA: Vector Network Analyzer

Models and modelling frameworks

Phenomenological models

- Cole–Cole (Cole & Cole 1941)
- CCM, Cole–Cole Conductivity Model (Tarasov & Titov 2013)
- Pelton model (PM) (Pelton et al. 1978)
- GDR, Generalized Dielectric Response (Wagner et al. 2011, 2013; Loewer et al. 2017)
- CPCM, Combined Permittivity and Conductivity Model (Loewer et al. 2017)

Mechanistic models

- Mechanistic EDL / Stern-layer framework (Leroy et al. 2017, 2025)
- Unified electrochemical framework (Revil 2013)
- Analytical model for interlayer cation dynamics in smectites (Rotenberg et al. 2005)

Mixing models

- Differential Effective Medium (DEM) upscaling framework (Okay et al. 2014)
- ABC-M, Augmented Broadband Complex Dielectric Mixture Model (Bore et al. 2018)
- CRIM, Complex Refractive Index Model (Cosenza et al. 2009)